

Mars Exploration Program Analysis Group (MEPAG)

July 1, 2026 – Letter from the Chair

Dear Mars community,

Thank you for your continued participation in MEPAG during this ongoing time of major change. While our activities are no longer funded by NASA, we aim to continue to be a reliable source of information and to provide a regular forum for the Mars science community to come together. I would like to personally thank all of the organizations within the community who have offered to help support MEPAG. We have been carefully evaluating these offers to ensure that we can utilize their help without impinging on our status as an independent, community-driven organization, as this remains our priority.

In case you missed it, we released [a statement on June 8](#) regarding several major concerns around sudden changes to MEP. Please see this statement for more details on (1) the impact of the inclusion of SkyFall in the MEP budget, (2) threats to Mars missions from SkyFall and ongoing budget negotiations, and (3) significant changes to management of federal assistance from OMB that will affect all NASA grants ([now implemented in ROSES](#)).

In this Letter from the Chair, I've provided an update on MEPAG activities, a request to review MEPAG findings from the April meeting, a NASA budget update, and a list of upcoming opportunities. If you have community opportunities that you would like us to consider including in a future letter (conferences, programs, etc.; please no job ads), please email me directly.

I would also like to express gratitude and congratulations to the MAVEN team for running an incredibly successful mission that generated a wealth of knowledge on the upper atmosphere and ionosphere of Mars. While the mission has concluded earlier than anticipated, its substantial legacy is already clear. We look forward to seeing MAVEN's work carried on by ESCAPEDE after Mars orbit insertion next year.

- Briony Horgan, MEPAG Chair (briony@purdue.edu)

Updates on MEPAG activities:

- We are currently working on finalizing plans for a website and a Zenodo document repository, but the [LPI hosted MEPAG site](#) should remain up and accessible for the foreseeable future.
- We are also currently finalizing plans for a new mailing list, which should include all MEPAG members on the original JPL-hosted list and will allow new signups. Updates coming soon.
- We anticipate that we will continue to host both virtual and hybrid meetings on or close to our typical semiannual schedule, and have a path forward for virtual meeting support. We are looking for free or low-cost venues for hosting our hybrid meeting in years to come, so please let me know if you have ideas.

MEPAG findings for review:

We have drafted [a set of MEPAG findings posted on Zenodo](#) based primarily on discussions at the April 2026 hybrid MEPAG meeting, but as noted in the slides, we have added some content based on more recent major changes to MEP (see below). While the findings are now publicly available, we will consider any suggested edits submitted by **Wednesday, July 15**. Please send any questions, comments, or concerns on the findings to me (Briony Horgan, briony@purdue.edu).

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Budget update:

The House Commerce, Justice, and Science (CJS) FY27 appropriations bill, which includes NASA funding, is awaiting a vote on the House floor, and cuts NASA SMD to \$6B from the current \$7.25B. The Senate CJS FY27 Appropriation Act is waiting on markup by the Senate Appropriations committee, but this won't happen until at least July 13 when the Senate returns from recess. While we don't know the Senate FY27 NASA funding levels yet, this year so far is playing out very similarly to last year, where the final SMD budget of \$7.25B was close to the Senate proposed level of \$7.3B. This was in large part due to the action of the community in support of NASA science.

I encourage you to reach out to your elected Representatives and Senators as well as the leaders of the Senate CJS Appropriations Subcommittee and full Senate Appropriations Committee ASAP, to ensure they have your input before the markup begins. Some resources for reaching out to the representatives are included [at the end of our June 8 statement](#).

Note that we are also waiting on congressional approval for NASA's proposed FY26 spending and operations plan, which is another opportunity for congress to place specific requirements on NASA programs.

Mars-relevant conference sessions this fall:

DPS - Spokane, WA, 25-30 October - late abstracts due July 30:

- Special session: 5 years of Perseverance rover exploration at Jezero Crater, Mars
- Special session: 20 years of MRO observing Mars from orbit

GSA - Denver, CO, 11-14 October - abstracts due August 6:

- Geomorphology and Landscape Evolution of Mars
- Boxwork and Fracture Halos [...] on Earth, Mars, and across the Solar System
- Planetary sample science: Unlocking the history of lunar, Martian, and asteroidal materials
- Geomorphology and Surface Processes Across the Solar System
- Impact Cratering: From the Earth into the Solar System
- Mineralogy in the Solar System
- Mineralogical Insights from Modern Spectroscopic Techniques
- Hydrothermal Processes Across the Solar System
- Shake and Bake: Volcanism and Tectonism across the Solar System

AGU - San Francisco, CA, 7-11 December - abstracts due August 5:

- P016 - Mars Surface Stories: Geology, Mineralogy, and Geochemistry
- P031 - The New Mars Underground IX: Maximizing Martian Subsurface Science Return
- P032 - The Surface and Subsurface of Mars as Seen from Orbit
- P022 - Processes in the Present-day Atmosphere of Mars
- P025 - Space Environments of Unmagnetized or Weakly Magnetized Solar System Bodies [...]
- P007 - Dynamic Exospheres of Terrestrial Bodies Throughout the Solar System and Beyond
- P028 - The Emergence of Life as a Planetary Process
- P021 - Planetary Volcanism: Processes and Observations

A banner image showing a view of Mars from space, with the reddish-orange surface and dark features visible against the blackness of space. The text "Mars Exploration Program Analysis Group (MEPAG)" is overlaid in white.

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Upcoming opportunities:

High-Resolution Imager Replacement Measurement Definition Team (HIREP-MDT)

From the JPL MPO newsletter: In the coming weeks, The Mars Exploration Program will charter a Measurement Definition Team (MDT) to support NASA in the formulation of requirements for an imaging payload to replenish and/or augment the HiRISE camera on MRO and accomplish tasks deemed necessary as precursors for future robotic and human exploration of Mars. [...] *The MPO will release further details soon.*

SkyFall Landing Site Workshops

From the JPL MPO newsletter: NASA Science Mission Directorate and the SkyFall project will be seeking science community input to select a landing site for the upcoming SkyFall mission to Mars. Given the shortened schedule before SkyFall launch in 2028, a modified approach to landing site input from the science community will be solicited, with two, one-day workshops separated by approximately one month being scheduled for later in 2026. The MEP will work with MEPAG to help coordinate community involvement in the workshops. Prior to the first workshop, an information package will be sent out to the community with background information to facilitate workshop discussions. All are encouraged to participate.